

Enhancement of Stability to Light in Field-Effect Transistors Based on Cumulenic *sp*-carbon Wires by Opaque Gating Electrodes

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Abstract — Cumulenic *sp*-hybridized carbon wires are receiving attention both for their excellent intrinsic electronic properties and for their potential exploitation as active semiconducting layers in large-area and flexible organic electronic devices. Such molecules exhibit a highly conjugated backbone chain, an equally high degree of electronic tunability, and offer an opportunity to better understand the elusive carbon allotrope known as carbyne. Among this class of molecules, tetraphenyl[3]cumulene ([3]Ph) has emerged as a reference point for applications in organic field-effect transistors (OFETs), owing to promising charge carrier mobility of $> 0.1 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$. However, photoinduced degradation of [3]Ph is a significant limitation to its possible future applications. Here, a gating strategy based on an opaque, spray-coated activated carbon (AC) based electrode is investigated to mitigate photodegradation in [3]Ph-based OFETs. Top-gate bottom-contact transistors have been fabricated and tested under various light conditions, comparing devices gated either by a transparent layer of PEDOT:PSS or opaque layers of AC, to probe light-induced degradation. Unlike PEDOT:PSS devices, the AC-gated transistors maintain consistent performance under light, demonstrating potential for practical applications of [3]Ph, similar cumulenes or even other photodegradable semiconductors in organic electronics.

Keywords — organic electronics, *sp*-carbon, cumulenes, activated carbon, photodegradation

I. INTRODUCTION

As the interest toward organic electronics grows and new applications are proposed, the quest for organic semiconductors (OSCs) providing both high device performance and stability becomes crucial. Among the most promising OSCs, cumulenic *sp*-hybridized carbon wires, also known as cumulenes, are progressively gaining attention [1-5]. Cumulenes are molecules featuring a highly conjugated backbone chain, with carbon atoms being bonded to each other through quasi-double bonds. They can be considered finite segments of the elusive carbon allotrope carbyne [6-8]. This ideal, infinite *sp*-carbon chain has the potential to display unparalleled properties, spanning from exceptional Young modulus [9] and thermal conductivity [10], to interesting charge transport properties [11]. The latter are related to the two degenerate, mutually orthogonal π -systems, which have no fixed nodal plane, allowing for a flexible delocalization of the charge [12]. Such a versatile material could play a pivotal role in future organic electronic

applications. However, the synthesis of carbyne has so far been unachievable due to the known reactivity of *sp*-carbon [13]. Currently, only finite cumulenes are available, and they partially retain carbyne electronic properties [14-15]. Besides, electronic properties in these molecules are highly tunable: through the modulation of the length of the *sp*-chain the energy gap can be modified [16-19], and the selection of the terminal groups affects solubility, energy levels, reactivity [20-22]. Although to a lower extent, reactivity is still an issue for finite molecules, as *sp*-hybridization is not an energetically favorable configuration for carbon [6, 20]. Shorter, bulky-group terminated molecules tend to be more stable. Accordingly, tetraphenyl[3]cumulene ([3]Ph) is particularly stable with respect to other cumulenes, both in air and in common organic solvents [20, 23], and therefore it has been successfully employed in thin films for p-type organic field effect transistors (OFETs) [24]. Field-effect mobilities up to $0.2 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$, with ideal transfer characteristic curves, and good operational stability over several measurements (both in air and in nitrogen atmosphere), have been demonstrated using this material [23]. One main weakness remains, though: [3]Ph is photosensitive, even more so when a current is flowing through it [23]. This represents a huge limitation in the practical applications this material can aspire to, because any risk of light exposure can result in a loss of reliability of the device. Encapsulation is a common method to protect OSCs from external factors, such as oxygen or humidity [25-27]. The question was if such a technique could work for cumulenes against light.

The main novelty of this work is a gating strategy designed to shield [3]Ph-based OFETs from light. The optimized [3]Ph OFET reported in [23] relies on a ink-jet printed PEDOT:PSS gate, in top-gate bottom-contact (TGBC) configuration. We replaced PEDOT:PSS with a spray-coated ink based on activated carbon (AC), which is conductive and can absorb near UV and visible light radiations. Both the PEDOT:PSS and the AC devices underwent the same cycle of measurements under different light conditions. Whereas the PEDOT:PSS devices showed decreased performances after a few seconds under white light, the AC transistors endured the photostress much better, with neither the transfer curve nor the field effect mobilities displaying any significant variation throughout the hour-long experiment. The increased stability of the device against light radiation was also confirmed by optical microscope inspection. This strategy turned out to be a simple, versatile, and effective solution to overcome photosensitivity in [3]Ph

and possibly other organic semiconducting layers adopted in OFETs, without requiring an additional light-blocking layer.

II. RESULTS

Two sets of samples, accommodating eight transistors each, were prepared for this work. One set was kept for the PEDOT:PSS reference devices, the second one to test the AC strategy. All the sixteen TGBC devices had the same structure (Fig. 1(a)), and were fabricated following the same procedure, except for the gate deposition. Gold interdigitated contacts were first evaporated on Corning glass after photolithographic patterning, obtaining a channel width of 2 cm and channel lengths of 5, 10, 20, and 40 μm (two devices for each length). The semiconductor, [3]Ph, was deposited on the whole substrate by bar-coating as described in [23], reaching a thickness of 20 nm. Parylene C was selected as dielectric and deposited by chemical vapor deposition, with a thickness of 520 nm. As for the gates, PEDOT:PSS was ink-jet printed on the channels area, achieving a thickness of 80 nm. The conductive AC-based ink was prepared as in [28] and spray-coated onto the Parylene layer through a shadow mask, ensuring the selective deposition of the ink on the channels only (Fig. 1(b)). To gate the eight devices of a substrate, a volume of 6 ml of ink was deposited to reach full opacity (50 μm of thickness), and block out light completely over an effective area of 1.84 cm^2 for the light range 200-1000 nm. All the above-mentioned steps were carried out in air. Then, the devices were moved into a controlled nitrogen atmosphere to decouple the effects of light and oxygen during the electrical characterization.

Both the PEDOT:PSS-gated and the AC-gated devices underwent the same measurement protocol: current-voltage (I - V) transfer characteristic curves were recorded at six fixed steps to acquire data about the transistors performance in different light conditions. The transfer curves were acquired by monitoring the modulation of the current while the gate voltage, V_{gs} , was swept between +5 V and -40 V. The drain voltage, V_{ds} , was set at -5 V and -40 V for the linear and saturation regimes, respectively. A first measurement was run prior to any light exposure as a reference, then a second measurement right after switching on a LED white light, that was shined perpendicularly on the transistors at a distance of 10 cm between the lamp and the sample. The light intensity was measured at different wavelengths: 1.94 W/m^2 at 200 nm, 0.95 W/m^2 at 370 nm, 0.65 W/m^2 at 450 nm, 0.53 W/m^2 at 590 nm, 0.45 W/m^2 at 730 nm, 0.36 W/m^2 at 1000 nm.. The third measurement was run with the light off again, the fourth one was carried out after the devices had been continuously exposed to light for 2 minutes, the fifth one after 90 minutes of light, and the last one after a 180-minute-long recovery in dark conditions.

The PEDOT:PSS devices decreased in performance starting from the very first light exposure. Fig. 1(c) displays saturation ($V_{\text{ds}} = -40$ V) transfer curves throughout the test for one of the 20 μm channel transistors, which will be discussed from now on. Not only did the current decrease as a consequence of the threshold shifting, but a marked hysteresis arose. This is likely due to the formation of electronic traps [29]. When the light source was removed, the hysteresis disappeared, but neither the threshold shift nor the on-current experienced a recovery. The fourth measurement, after the sample had endured 2 minutes of light, further underlined the detrimental effects of light on unshielded

[3]Ph devices. As expected, the fifth measurement, run after 90 minutes of light exposure, greatly affected the devices, with current dropping by two orders of magnitude with respect to the earliest curve. The last measurement confirmed that irreversible photodegradation occurred in the semiconductor. The gradual decrease in the off current is most likely due to oxygen release, caused by the long stay in nitrogen atmosphere, rather than any effects from light. Indeed, oxygen can act as a p-type dopant in organic semiconductors such as [3]Ph [30-31]. The inset in Fig. 1(c) shows a microscopic image of the thin film before light exposure (top) and at the end of the experiment (bottom): large and connected crystalline grains turned into smaller structures, separated by voids and apparently more disordered regions.

The AC-gated transistors showed a comparable behavior before light exposure, demonstrating that AC can provide effective gating. Furthermore, AC devices were more resilient than PEDOT:PSS ones throughout the photostress experiment. Fig. 1(d) refers to a 20 μm channel transistor, equivalent to that in Fig. 1(c), if not for the gate material. No hysteresis could be detected, and the currents were stable regardless of the light exposure, confirming that the AC gate managed to shield the [3]Ph thin film from light. After the long recovery step, the transistors experienced a drop in the off current and a slight shift of the threshold voltage, which is again consistent with a de-doping process. As further proof of the successful adoption of the opaque AC gate electrode, the inset in Fig. 1(d) shows a pristine [3]Ph film, with no signs of degradation.

The above results were discussed for two specific 20 μm channel transistors, either gated by PEDOT:PSS or AC, but are representative of, and fully consistent with all the other seven transistors gated by the corresponding electrode, irrespectively of the channel length. Table 1 outlines the mean device parameters extracted from eight devices (channel lengths: 5, 10, 20, and 40 μm), before and after the light cycling, for the two types of gates. Overall, AC devices were thoroughly tested, and they consistently endured the photostress. The performance prior to light exposure are on average worse than that of PEDOT:PSS transistors in terms of currents and field-effect mobility. This has likely to do with PEDOT:PSS being more conductive. AC sheet resistance stands at about 250 $\text{k}\Omega/\text{sq}$ [28], which is three orders of magnitude higher than PEDOT:PSS [32]. This might lead to dielectric depolarization, hindering charge transport along the channel. However, the total inability of PEDOT:PSS devices to sustain white light when operating, prevents them from most applications. The AC gating strategy as it is, requires optimization to match or even outperform PEDOT:PSS, but it is a good start in taking the study of *sp*-carbon materials towards actual applications.

TABLE I.

Gate	Stage	μ_{sat} (cm^2/Vs)	$V_{\text{th,sat}}$ (V)	On/off ratio
PEDOT:PSS	Pre	0.067	-6.9	$\sim 10^5$
	Post	$0.075 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-10.3	$\sim 10^4$
AC	Pre	0.003	-7.1	$\sim 10^4$
	Post	0.003	-8.3	$\sim 10^4$

Table 1. Mean saturation field effect mobility, μ_{sat} , saturation threshold voltage, $V_{\text{th,sat}}$, and saturation on/off current ratio extracted from the devices gated with PEDOT:PSS and AC, before and after the light exposure.

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic representation of the top-gate bottom-contact OFETs reported in this work. (b) Deposition of the AC gate by selective spray-coating of the ink on the devices active area, its light-shielding effect, and the percentage transmittance of the two gates. (c)-(d) Saturation ($V_{ds} = -40$ V) drain current curves of a 20 μm channel transistor, gated by PEDOT:PSS (c) and AC (d), at different steps of the experiment. Insets: [3]Ph film images before and after the light cycles.

III. CONCLUSION

The study of cumulenic sp -hybridized carbon wires has recently become appealing for their potential as high-performance organic semiconductors. In particular, thin films of [3]Ph stand out for their good performance in OFETs. However, photodegradation limits [3]Ph applications. In this work, we proposed a gating strategy using spray-coated AC opaque electrodes in TGBC [3]Ph devices to address this issue. Transparent gates allow [3]Ph transistors to be functional as long as these are kept in the dark, but irreversible degradation signs in the semiconducting film readily show up upon light exposure. On the contrary, opaque, black layers of conductive AC are efficient in blocking the light exposure of the active area, so that the devices have stable performance even after light exposure longer than an hour. This very effective approach has the advantage of simple implementation, requiring only a

masked spraying process. Optimization is necessary to further improve the devices gated by AC, but overcoming photodegradation to such an extent is an important step in the stabilization of cumulenes thin films for microelectronics, and should find relevant applications also for electronic devices based on sp^2 -conjugated semiconductors.

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